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INTRODUCTION

Global changes in the world, the rapid development of science and technology, and the environment of the information society based on the development of information technologies have impact on the education system. One of the main tasks of today's regularly implemented educational reforms and innovative processes is fully adaptation to the features of the digitization process. The urgency of improving the cooperation of social institutions in the management of the educational system at the international level is becoming more and more obvious. Therefore, the development of interactive technologies of informatization of educational processes in higher education institutions, special attention to the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms

DIGITALIZATION OF THE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The article describes issues based on introducing digital technologies into the education system. The development of digital technologies in the field of education is dictated by relevance and is supported at the state level and by the general public. Digitalization is a new social situation with the main changes in education which are related to the digitalization of education. In the process of digitalization, the very structure of education and the organization of the educational process are fundamentally changing. The use of new information and communication technologies is the initial condition for the further development of digital pedagogy.

of creating an integrative educational environment are among the urgent tasks. The current stage of world development is characterized by the continuous growth of the volume of scientific information. Methodically, the digitalization of the education system is based on new educational standards, using a new competence-based approach. We need a tool for creating educational materials, a tool for the effective delivery of content and knowledge of students for effective teaching. Universities use a two-component information and educational environment that combines the resources of international educational platforms with the content of their developments, which contributes to the development of their own IT potential. It is necessary to introduce a modern digital base of the educational process - the information and

educational environment (IEE). The implementation of an effective IEE is the basis for the development of any university. The digitalization of higher education will change the qualification requirements for the teaching staff. Teachers are beginning to use digital technologies that make their work easier. Universities began to master new formats of knowledge transfer, primarily online courses.

METHODS AND ANALYSIS

Changes in education associated with the digitalization of education will lead to profound changes in the labor market. This is an occasion for the further reorganization of the educational process. Electronic library resources from all universities and educational materials from the best teachers in the world will be available to all students. In the coming years, such systems for the automatic translation of texts and speech from any language will be developed and implemented. Such actions will lead to a serious restructuring of the educational process and a change in the role of the teacher, who in the future will not explain this or that material but will help find the location of this material and understand it. There is a lot of talk about the digitalization of educational institutions today. There are predictions that the online education platform will supplant universities. Universities began to master new formats of knowledge transfer, primarily online courses [4].

Creating an electronic information educational environment of an educational institution is not a purely technical issue, but for this it is necessary to use the scientific-methodical, organizational and

pedagogical capabilities of the institution based on a systematic approach. [2]

The use of modern information and telecommunication technologies in the educational system is carried out in the following directions:

- information and telecommunication technologies as an object of study, that is, students acquire general skills regarding new information technologies, their components, and fields of use;
- information and telecommunication technologies as a means of learning, that is, students are taught based on modern information and pedagogical technologies, and lectures, practical and laboratory exercises are organized on the basis of modern computer software tools;
- as a means of managing the educational process, i.e. creating a system of information, analysis and forecasting to increase the efficiency of all work activities of the educational institution, including educational, spiritual-educational and scientific-research works;
- as a means of carrying out scientific and pedagogical research of students and professors, that is, creating and implementing modern information systems to increase the effectiveness of scientific research and pedagogical research among professors and students at the educational institution.

A pedagogue working with information technology tools must meet the following competency requirements:

- The fact that it embodies the qualities of media competence;

DISCUSSIONS

Media competence is a relatively new term in our educational system, and it includes the ability to transfer and evaluate media information in various forms, learn, and

convey it. Media education means the process of development of a person through mass media. Professor A.B. Fedorov media education in the modern world for the purpose of forming a culture of communication with mass information, mass communication (media) for the purpose of applying creative, communicative skills, critical thinking, comprehensive perception, interpretation, analysis, and evaluation of media texts to various forms of self-expression using media technology) builds as a process of personal development with the help of tools and materials.

- To have the ability to create electronic textbooks and to freely work with them;
- Ability to freely work in programs such as ZOOM, Google meet, Google disk, and Camtasia studio;
- Enriching the distance education platform with creative innovations and others.

General pedagogic principles of personnel training for informatization of education can be given as follows:

- the invariance of the basic training in relation to the professional orientation, its orientation to information, communication, general cultural aspects, its compatibility with the current level of development of the information society;
- specialization of the training of pedagogic personnel, i.e. orientation to the introduction of the possibilities of information and communication technologies in a specific subject;
- differentiation of pedagogic personnel training, its orientation to personal preference, professional interest and characteristics of students.

In order to implement the principles of professional and specialized training of pedagogues and the principles of a

differentiated approach, the following should be reflected in the development of the structure of the educational program:

- the state of the process of informing the society in the study programs;
- theoretical foundations of education informatization;
- the main organizers of the activity of pedagogic personnel regarding the use of information and communication technologies in a specific subject in study programs;
- methodological support of independent educational activities. It can be assumed that the widespread introduction of educational programs that can meet these requirements will create a mechanism for eliminating a number of the above-mentioned shortcomings.

Now it is difficult to imagine organizing the educational process without using the possibilities of computer technology. The simplicity of the interface included in the computer software provides an opportunity for pedagogues to effectively use modern information technologies.

Therefore, one of the promising directions of introduction of modern information technologies in education is computer modeling of events and processes. Computer models are a great help to harmonize the content of the traditional lesson and for the teacher to display many effects on the computer screen, to organize new, non-traditional educational activities of the students.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we can say that it is appropriate to perform the following tasks in order to further increase the efficiency of higher education institutions:

- development of a mechanism for continuous improvement of media

competence of educational subjects (on YouTube and other social networks support at the state level to increase the number of video lessons on the use of various ICT programs in the Uzbek language);

- control and practical support of the process of provision of necessary modern technical equipment for educational institutions, the establishment of systematic operation of internet

connection and technical equipment even in remote areas;

- wide implementation of electronic management systems and sharp reduction of red tape and time-consuming unnecessary documents;

- Development of mechanisms to increase the responsibility of subjects on the distance education platform, as well as on all social networks.

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